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Molecular characterization of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* by SDS-PAGE and plasmid Analysis

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Abstract

Lactobacillus acidophilus is well known because of its probiotic role hence gain importance in food and nutrition. Keeping in view the importance of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* there was dire need to identify the strain accurately. Phenotypically identified 27 strains were characterized by SDS-PAGE and plasmid profile. SDS-PAGE analysis had shown that most of the strains were strongly coupled with little variation. Only two strains do not belong to any cluster showing the authenticity of SDS-PAGE. Further Plasmid profile of DNA of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* represent the characteristics pattern, and among 27 strains 15 isolates showed the presence of plasmid. Based on number and size of plasmid the strains are grouped into three distinct groups. A combination of SDS-PAGE and plasmid analysis has been shown a practical method to use for identification of *Lactobacillus* at species level. However the conventional method should be combined with genotypic method for a thorough analysis of strain.

Introduction

The role of lactic acid bacteria in food and beverage industry cannot be ignored. They not only used as starter culture in the development of the product but in addition to this have probiotic impact on the human health. (Klaenmhammar *et al.*; 2005). *Lactobacillus acidophilus* is a probiotic strain that had been used over the years not only in the formulation of milk, yogurt but also in dry supplements and juices due to its probiotic nature (Sander and Klaenmhammar, 2001). These friendly bacteria live in the gastrointestinal tract and produce lactic acid, hydrogen peroxide and other by-products that make the environment hostile for undesirable microorganism (anonymus 2004; Chou and Weiner, 1999). The importance of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* necessitates the characterization of strain by the most reliable source so that probiotic health products contain the same *Lactobacillus* strains that have been mentioned on the products. (Tykken *et al.*; 1999).

Many approaches have been used for the precise identification of microorganism. Phenotypic methods are principle method for identification but are time taking and sometimes are also effected by environmental condition, and reliable method is therefore required to deal with a large number of isolates. (Moreira *et al.*, 2005).

There have been major advances in recent years in the characterization of bacteria by molecular methods (Reid 1990). Among these methods, protein fingerprinting by SDS-PAGE is considered a useful tool for identification. The plasmid profile pattern ascertained by agarose gel electrophoresis has been used successfully to resolve the taxonomic status of the lab (Davis *et al.*, 1981). overall the development of PCR based methodologies has provided simple and rapid tool for identifying bacteria (Wang *et al.*, 1996). Some of these methods rely on amplification of the PCR product by using species-specific primers. Such advances in molecular methodology provide great potential for rapid and reliable quality control of probiotic products (Mccartney; 2002).

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The fast and reliable quality control of probiotic products is crucial in order to obtain functional and safe probiotic products. So current study relies on the identification of Phenotypically identified strains of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* by fingerprinting of protein and plasmid profile.

MATERIAL and METHODS

Bacterial strains

Twenty seven identified strains of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* were obtained from the stock culture collection bank of food biotechnology Laboratory, Department of Food Technology, University of Arid Agriculture Rawalpindi. Cultures were maintained in MRS broth containing 20% glycerol at -20°C. These cultures were propagated twice in their respective medium at 37°C. After activation, the strains were then subjected to molecular characterization.

Protein profile analysis

Protein profile analysis of bacterial strains was done by SDS –PAGE as described by Laemmli (1970). The procedure was used after some modifications.

Preparation of bacterial sample

Two ml of culture was inoculated in 10 ml of broth (culture is activated in their respective broth) and was incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The cells were harvested by centrifugation at 8000 rpm for 1 minute the pellet was washed in 200 µl of stacking buffer (1M Tris pH 6.8., 20% SDS) and was resuspended in 10 µl of the same buffer and was vortexed. Then 80 µl of sample buffer (1M Tris pH 6.8., 20% SDS, 20% glycerol, 10% β-mercaptoethanol and 0.005% Bromophenol blue) and 605 µl of β-mercaptoethanol was added to the preparation. The sample was kept in boiling water for 7 minutes and was immediately shifted to ice. Finally it was centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 1 minute.

Preparation of SDS-PAGE

For electrophoresis, 4.5% stacking gel and 12.5% resolving gel was prepared. 15-20µl of each sample was loaded on the gel. Five µl of protein molecular weight marker (116 k Da to 14.4 kDa) of fermantas was used as standard. The gel was run firstly at 80 V and then at 100 V for 3 hours by using a running buffer (TRIS 0.25 M, Glycine 14.4% and SDS 10%, pH 8.3). Gel was then fixed in fixator (methanol 40% (v/v), glacial acetic acid 7% (v/v)) and was stained in a solution containing 0.1% (w/v) coomassie blue, 10% (v/v) acetic acid and 40% (v/v) methanol. De-staining was done in a solution containing 10% (v/v) acetic acid and 45% (v/v) methanol.

Cluster Analysis

The dendrogram was constructed by the Hierarchical cluster analysis. All the analysis was carried out by statistical package SPSS version 10.0.

Plasmid isolation

Plasmid isolation was done by using Alkaline Lysis Procedure as described by Sambrook *et al.* (1989)

Preparation of Cells

Two ml of culture was inoculated in 10 ml of broth (culture was activated in their respective broth) and was incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Next day 1.5 ml of culture was poured into a microfuge tube and centrifuge to get pellet. Pellet was washed in 40 µl of ice-cold Alkaline Lysis solution I (Glucose 50mm, Tris-C1 25 mm and EDTA 10mm). Two hundred µl of Alkaline Lysis Solution II (SDS 1%, NaOH 0.2 N) and 150 µl of ice-cold Alkaline Lysis solution III (5M Na –acetate, 60 ml, glacial acetic acid, 11.5 ml, and water, 28.5 ml). The lysate was obtained in the form of supernatant, from which plasmid was precipitated by using phenol: chloroform mix.

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The aqueous upper layer was transferred to a fresh tube. Nucleic acid This variation from the supernatant by adding two volumes of ethanol at room temperature. Precipitated nucleic acid was recovered by centrifugation. The supernatant was removed, and DNA was washed by using 70% ethanol. Before dissolving the nucleic acid, beads of ethanol were removed that were present on the sides of the tubes. For this purpose tube was placed open at room temperature for 5-10 minutes until the ethanol had evaporated and no fluid was visible in the tube. Then nucleic acid was dissolved in 30 μ l of TE (pH 8.0).and DNA solution was stored at -20 °C.

Agarose Gel Electrophoresis

Agarose gel electrophoresis was conducted on 0.7% Agarose in horizontal mini electrophoresis by using TBE Buffer (Tris, Boric acid and EDTA ph 8.0) at 70V.10 μ l of DNA sample was mixed with 2 μ l of Bromophenol blue tracking dye and poured in wells. Lambda Hind 111 DNA molecular weight marker (23130-564 bp) was used as a standard for molecular weight determination. The gel was stained with ethidium bromide 0.5 μ g/ml and was observed under UV transilluminator for the presence of plasmid band.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

The following study was conducted in an effort to confirm the identification of Phenotypically identified twenty seven strains of *lactobacillus acidophilus* by using molecular techniques, including sodium dodecyl sulphate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) and plasmid analysis.

The whole-cell protein profile of twenty seven identified strains of *lactobacillus acidophilus* is shown in fig 1.these strains were firstly characterized by visual comparison of their electrophoretic pattern, and it has been viewed that the strains produced a varying number of protein bands as numbers vary from 9-11. It is evident from the other data that *lactobacillus acidophilus* produced six prominent bands of 25, 31, 45, 50, 0 and 65 K Da while some minor bands were also recorded at 14.4, 18, 68, 7 and 120 K Da .These results are supported by Perez *et al.*, 2000 who also pointed out four prominent bands of 40, 45, 50 and 60 K Da.

In present study majority of protein, the profile was similar among all strains however some minor differences may be due to genetic variation coupled with the growth condition of propagation and difference in protein profile represent the corresponding difference in their genotype.

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Fig 1. SDS-PAGE of cell-free protein extract of *lactobacillus acidophilus* strain. Lane 1 molecular weight marker, lane 2 to 8 *lactobacillus acidophilus* Z3, R18, La2, A17R, A10R, A22R, and LT1.

For further comparison of overall similarity of protein pattern of different strains, cluster analysis was done between two different groups of *lactobacillus acidophilus* and *lactobacillus bulgaricus* by similarity dendrogram. After the numerical comparison of resulting electrophoretic protein fingerprints. It has been observed that two strains fell into two well-delineated clusters representing the resemblance with the data obtained by Pot *et al.*;1993 who examined the protein fingerprints of different strains of *lactobacillus* through cluster analysis and found each group represents a specific cluster. Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. cluster analysis between lactobacillus acidophilus and lactobacillus bulgaricus

The occurrence of strains in different clusters reflect the differences in their protein profile, although the position of many bands was similar difference might be in their relative intensity similar views are shared by Gomez-Zavaglia *et al.* (1999) who constructed the similarity dendrogram of *lactobacillus acidophilus*. Based on this, SDS-PAGE could be considered as reliable method for identification of *lactobacillus acidophilus* since cluster analysis clearly differentiate *lactobacillus acidophilus* from *lactobacillus bulgaricus* on the basis of varying number of protein bands as 20-25 bands were observed in *lactobacillus bulgaricus* as compared to 8-11 bands in *lactobacillus acidophilus* instead that positions of majority bands were similar these results are comparable by Teanpaisan and Dahlen (2006) who determined different number of protein bands between two strains. They also confirm their results through PCR and revealed that two different categories are due to genetic heterogeneity between these strains

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Further within group dendrogram was constructed to confirm any variation present .It has been observed that there was variation in terms of their protein profile within the same strains as shown in fig 3. In general at a correlation of 0.34, Seven clusters are formed that represent different degrees of overall similarity among the strains of *lactobacillus acidophilus*. The strains having the same position of bands are grouped together in one cluster

Table 1.

No of clusters	Sub clusters	No of strains	Total number of strains	Designation of strains
I	I a	1	7	La2
	I b	6		ID3, A4R, A5R, A17R, M4, and L15
II	II a	1	3	J1
	II b	2		ID8, A10R
III	III a	1	4	R16
	III b	3		R15, M3and R10
IV	IV a	2	2	R18 and Z3
V	V a	1	3	L18
	V b	2		A30R and A24R
VI	VI a	1	1	I3
VII	VII a	1	4	J3
	VII b	3		R20, J2 and F11

From the overall view, it has been observed that 15 isolates are strongly coupled at a correlation of 0.98 and must not be considered as different strains, but they are the isolates of the same strains. Two strains represented 80 % similarities, and two strains show 50% similarities. 5 isolates are associated at 0.6 correlation. Only two isolates LT1 and A22R does not belong to any cluster representing the authenticity of SDS- PAGE because protein profile on SDS-PAGE found to be different and specific for each strain similar views are shared by Gatti *et al*; 1997 who determined the specificity of SDS-PAGE for different lactic acid bacteria .so based on these results it is recommended a valuable tool for identification of *lactobacillus acidophilus* as supported by Teanpaisan and Dahlen (2006) who considered the SDS-PAGE as valuable tool for identification of *lactobacillus acidophilus* from *L.crispatus* and *L. Bulgaricus*.

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The strains were further screened for plasmid profile. The plasmid profile of DNA in *Lactobacillus acidophilus* was diverse and characteristic pattern was observed. The distinct number of the plasmid in the strains varied from 1-3. These plasmids range in size between 1.3 to 23 kb as shown in table 2. By comparing the plasmid profile it was possible to assemble 15 isolates into three groups with identical or nearly identical plasmids profile. Group I contained the only one plasmid that ranges in size between 20-23 kb. However Lin and Savage (1985) were able to isolate only one plasmid of 2.6 M Da. This variation in size may be due to genetic variation and due to difference of methods applied for extraction of DNA. Second group contained the plasmids of very low molecular weight. Group III contained three number of plasmids that shows that even number of plasmids can be present in the *Lactobacillus acidophilus* as Vescova *et al.* 1982) observed three to five number of plasmid in type strains of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. The possible reason for variation of plasmid number might be the failure of extraction under laboratory condition due to continuous cultivation of strains that is responsible for mutation or complete loss of plasmid. Moreover other possible reason may be the genetic heterogeneity as well as sensitivity of methods used for extraction of plasmids. The data suggest that all members within same plasmid profile group can be considered as variants of same ancestor as suggested by Josephen and Nielsen (1988). Consequently plasmid profile might use full in grouping isolates with identical morphology and physiological properties also supported by Rodtong and Tannock (1993) where plasmid typing of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* has been suggested as taxonomic tool.

Groups	No of strains	No of plasmids	Approximate size (kb)
I	7	1	23
II	5	2	2.5, 1.3
III	3	3	23, 2.3, 1.3

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Fig 3. plasmid profiles of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. M in each group representing the marker Lambda DNA HindIII(2313 to 564 bp)

Conclusion

pro biotic cultures have gained importance because of their health benefits to human. An impressive number of microbial species considered as probiotic however LAB are considered \important with respect to food and nutrition. For having true to type products a combination of molecular techniques have been revealed as a practical approach for identification of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. however in addition to SDS-PAGE and plasmid profile the amplification of 16srRNA by using specific primer is also considered as valuable tool for authenticity of all analysis as done in this study too (not part of this article) however principal identification is still based on microbiological and biochemical methods and for thorough analysis conventional identification method should be combined with genotyping methods as further sequencing of 16srRNA can be done.

References

- i. Anonymous. 2004. *Lactobacillus acidophilus*.
(<http://dwb.unl.edu/teacher/nsf/c11links/www.bact.wise.eduscienceed/lactobacillusacidophilus.htm>).
- ii. Chou, L and B. Weimer. 1999. Isolation and characterization of acid and bile-tolerant isolates from strains of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. *J. Dairy Sci.*, 82: 23-31.
- iii. Anderson, D. G. and L. L. McKay. 1983. Simple and rapid method for isolating large plasmid DNA from *Lactic Streptococci*. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.*, 46: 549-552. .
- iv. Daniel, J., O. Sullivan and T. R. Klaenhammer 1993. Rapid mini-prep isolation of high-quality plasmid DNA from *Lactococcus* and *Lactobacillus* species. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.*, 59 (8): 2730-2733.
- v. Davies, F. L., H. M. Underwood and M. J. Gasson 1981. The value of plasmid profiles for strain identification of *Lactic acid Streptococci* and the relationship between *Streptococcus lactis* 712, ML 3 and C2. *J. Appl. Bacteriol.*, 51: 325-337.
- vi. Felten, A., C. Barreau, C. Bizet, P.H Lagrange and A. Phillippon. 1999. *Lactobacillus* species identification, H₂O₂ production, and antibiotic resistance and correlation with human clinical status. *J. Clin. Microbiol.*, 37 (3):729-733.

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- vii. Gatti, M., E. Fornasari, and E. Neviani. 1997. Cell- wall protein profiles of dairy thermophilic *Lactobacilli*. *Lett. Appl. Microbiol.*, 25: 345-348.
- viii. Gomez-Zavaglia, A., A. Abraham, S. Giorgeri and G. Deantoni. 1999. Application of polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis and capillary gel electrophoresis to the analysis of *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* whole cell proteins. *J. Dairy Sci.*, 82: 870-877.
- ix. Josephsen, J. and E. W. Nielsen. 1988. Plasmid profiles and bacteriophage sensitivity of bacteria of cheddar starter used for five years without rotation. *Milchissenschaft. Milk Sci.*, 43 (4): 219-223.
- x. Klaenkammer, T. R. And S. M. Sutherland. 1980. Detection of plasmid deoxyribonucleic acid in an isolate of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. *Appl. Environ Microbiol.*, 39 (3): 671-674.
- xi. Klaenhammer, T. R., R. barangou, B. Logan Buck, M. Andrea Azcarate-Peril, E. Altermann. 2005. Genomic features of Lactic acid bacteria effecting bioprocessing and health. *FEMS Microbiol. Reviews*. 29: 393-409.
- xii. Laemmli, U. K. 1970. Cleavage of structural proteins during the assembly of the head of bacteriophage T4. *Nature*. 227: 680-685.
- xiii. Leisner, J. B. Pot, H. Christensen, G. Rusul, J.E Olsen, B. W. Wee, K. Muhammad and H. M. Ghazali. 1998. Identification of Lactic acid bacteria from chili Bo, a Malaysian food ingredient. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.*, 65 (2): 599-605.
- xiv. Lin, J. H. C. And D. C. Savage. 1985. Cryptic plasmids in *Lactobacillus* strains isolated from the murine gastrointestinal tract. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.*, 49 (4): 1004-1006.
- xv. McCartney, A. L. 2002. Application of molecular biological methods for studying probiotics and the gut flora. *Brit. J. Nutr.*, 88 (1): 29-38.
- xvi. Moreira, J. L. S., R. M. Mota, M.F. Horta, S. M. R. Teixeira, E. Neumann, J. R. Nicoli and A. C. Nunes. 2005. Identification to the species level of *Lactobacillus* isolated in probiotic prospecting studies of human, animal or food origin by 16S-23S rRNA restriction profiling. (<http://www.biomedcentral.com/1471-2180/5/15>).
- xvii. Perez, G., E. Cardell and V. Zarte. 2000. Protein fingerprinting as a complementary analysis to classical phenotyping for the identification of Lactic acid bacteria from Tenerife cheese. *Lait.*, 80: 589-600.
- xviii. Pot, B., C. Hertel, W. Ludwig, P. Descheemaeker, K. Kersters and K. H. Schleifer. 1993. Identification and classification of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *L. Gasseri* and *L. Johnsonii* strains by SDS-PAGE and rRNA-targeted oligonucleotide probe hybridization. *J. Gen. Microbiol.*, 139 (3): 513-17.
- xix. Reid, G. 1999. The scientific bases for probiotic strains of *Lactobacillus*. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.*, 65: 3763-3766.
- xx. Rodtong, S. and G. W. Tannock. 1993. Differentiation of *Lactobacillus* strains by ribotyping. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.*, 59: 3480-3484.
- xxi. Sambrook, J., E. Tsakalidou, J. Metaxopoulos and G. Kalantzopoulos. 1989. *Molecular cloning*, 2nd ed. CSH Laboratory press, New York.
- xxii. Sanders M. E. and T. R. Klaenhammer. 2001. The Scientific basis of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* NCFM functionality as a probiotic. *J. Dairy Sci.*, 84: 319-331.

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- xxiii. Teanpaisan, R and G. Dahlen. 2006. Use of polymerase chain reaction techniques and sodioum dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis for differentiation of oral *Lactobacillus* species. *Oral Microbiol. Immunol.*, 21: 79-83.
- xxiv. Tsakalidou, W., W. Manolopoulou, E. Kabaraki, E. Zidou, B. Pot, K. Kersters and G. Kalantzopoulos. 1994. The combined use of whole-cell protein extracts for the identification (SDS-PAGE) and enzyme activity screening of Lactic acid bacteria isolated from traditional Greek dairy products. *Sys.Appl. Microbiol.*, 17: 444-458.
- xxv. Tynkkynen, S., R. Satokari, M. Saarela, T. Mattila-Sandholm and M. Saxelin. 1999. Comparison of ribotyping, randomly amplified polymorphic DNA analysis, and pulsed-field gel electrophoresis in typing of *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* and *L. Casei* strains. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.*, 65 (9): 3908-3914.
- xxvi. Vescovo, M., L. Morelli, and V. Bottazzi. 1982. Drug resistance plasmids in *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and *Lactobacillus reuteri*. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.*, 43 (1): 50-56.
- xxvii. Wilhelm, A. H., P. Haberer, R. Geisen, J. Bjorkroth and U. Schillinger. 2001. Taxonomy and important features of probiotic microorganisms in food and nutrition. *Ameri. J. Clin. Nutr.*, 73 (2): 365-373.
- xxviii. Wang, R. F., W. W. Cao, and C. E. Cernigil. 1996. PCR detection and quantitation of predominant anaerobic bacteria in human and animal fecal samples. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.*, 62 (4): 1242-1247
- xxix. Zhong, W., K. Millsap, H. B. Hobrzanska, and G. Reid. 1998. Differentiation of *Lactobacillus* species by molecular typing. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.*, 64 (7): 2418-2423.